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28 **1. Introduction**

29 Current society needs a large volume of fresh water to keep its present lifestyle,
30 whether for irrigation, to generate electricity or to fulfill industrial, domestic and
31 recreational needs. This, coupled with the exponential population growth, has caused
32 the installation of a great number of infrastructures to collect and use this resource
33 (Nilsson et al., 2005).

34 These structures are usually cross-sectional to the river, breaking its longitudinal
35 connectivity and blocking the movement of some animals such as fish, which require
36 different environments for some of the most important stages of their life cycle
37 (Porcher and Travade, 2002; Branco et al., 2013). In the best case scenario, the impact
38 of these barriers will cause the diminution in abundance of some species and, in the
39 worst case scenario, their disappearance (Larinier, 2001; Lucas et al., 2001; Branco et
40 al., 2012). It is in this context that fish passes or fishways arise to facilitate the free
41 movement of fish fauna through these obstacles (Clay, 1995; FAO/DVWK, 2002;
42 Larinier, 2002a).

43 Fish passes are a clear example of ecological engineering, since they are civil
44 engineering devices, which can be natural-like according to their type, with a
45 efficiency, understood as the proportion of fish from a given population that attempt
46 and succeed in surpassing the obstacle, associated to their hydrodynamic variables
47 (discharge, velocity, depth, power, turbulence fields, etc.) and a combination of
48 swimming capacity, behavior, and motivation of fish (Bermúdez et al., 2010; Sanz-
49 Ronda et al., 2015a). In addition, these hydrodynamic variables depend on
50 environmental parameters, such as fluctuation in water levels upstream and

51 downstream of the structure (Fuentes-Pérez et al., 2014).

52 In Europe, the installation of fishways has increased since the implementation of the
53 Water Framework Directive (European Commission, 2000). However, the efficiency of
54 these structures has been questioned due to the wide diversity of fish species and the
55 great unknowns regarding their swimming abilities, migration periods, and motivation
56 (Bunt et al., 2012; Williams et al., 2012). Therefore, biological and ecological studies
57 are essential, particularly in less studied species, such as potamodromous species
58 (Roscoe and Hinch, 2010; Bunt et al., 2012; Katopodis and Williams, 2012; Silva et al.,
59 2012). In recent years, in the Iberian Peninsula, this knowledge gap has been
60 addressed by a number of studies (Santos et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2012; Alexandre et
61 al., 2013; Branco et al., 2013; Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015a, among others). From a
62 practical viewpoint, all of these studies should show a correct hydraulic
63 characterization in order to enable the application of the collected knowledge to new
64 designs.

65 The most common fishways are pool-type fishways (Clay, 1995; Martínez de Azagra,
66 1999; FAO/DVWK, 2002; Puertas et al., 2012). They consist of a sloping-floor channel
67 divided by weirs, cross-walls, or baffles into a series of pools, distributing the height to
68 be crossed by the fish (H) into several smaller water drops (ΔH) (Larinier, 2002a). A
69 further classification of pool-type fishways is possible according to the type of
70 connection between pools, being one of the most popular those composed by
71 submerged notch and orifices (SNOF) (Larinier, 2008) (Fig. 1).

72

a)

b)

c)

73 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of a submerged notch and orifice fishway (SNOF) pool, used in
 74 the present study: (a) plant, (b) longitudinal section, (c) cross section. Symbols are defined in
 75 the notation section.

76 This type of fishways can have two different performances or regimes, streaming or
 77 plunging, depending on whether the downstream water level (h_2) influences or not,
 78 respectively, upstream water level (h_1) (Rajaratnam et al., 1988; Larinier, 2002a).
 79 Likewise, it is also possible to define different sub-regimes within these two main
 80 performances (Ead et al., 2004).

81 Pool and weir type fishways have been commonly designed with notches working
 82 under plunging conditions (Kim, 2001; Yagci, 2010; Santos et al., 2012). However, in
 83 SNOF, the notch is designed to operate in a streaming regimen, which has been shown
 84 to enhance the upstream movements of species like Iberian barbel (*Luciobarbus*
 85 *bocagei*), Iberian chub (*Squalius pyrenaicus*) or Iberian nase (*Pseudochondrostoma*
 86 *duriense*), and seems to be more suitable for rivers with fish with wide morpho-
 87 ecological traits (Silva et al., 2009; Branco et al., 2013; Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015b).
 88 Furthermore, SNOF shows additional benefits such as alternating submerged orifices
 89 from side to side. This orifice configuration has shown higher rates of passages than
 90 other configurations for the Iberian barbel (Silva et al., 2012).

91 Previous reports have widely studied similar type of designs using either classical weir-

92 discharge equations (Martínez de Azagra, 1999; Kim, 2001; FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier,
93 2002a; Boiten and Dommerholt, 2006; Santos et al., 2012) or dimensionless
94 relationships (Rajaratnam et al., 1989; Ead et al., 2004; Yagci, 2010); however, these
95 studies were always performed under uniform operational conditions (same mean
96 water level (h_0) and ΔH in all pools). This simplification limits the interpretation of their
97 behavior once they are installed because fishways will work under changing non-
98 uniform conditions which may decrease their efficiency (Fuentes-Pérez et al., 2014),
99 due to large variations in the hydrological regime of rivers, as it is the case in the
100 Mediterranean regions (Gasith and Resh, 1999), or due to an inaccurate execution.
101 That is to say, the boundary conditions and its geometry will determine not only the
102 regimen of the fishway (plunging, streaming or mixed) but also the water level
103 distributions (non-uniform or uniform profiles), which may modify the observed
104 efficiency in laboratory models.

105 In order to solve the above mentioned issues, this study aims to define the operational
106 conditions of submerged notch and orifice fishways both under different regimens and
107 uniform and non-uniform performances, modifying the classical formulation that has
108 widely been used to describe their behavior. This will allow to describe and predict
109 their functioning, i.e. the hydraulic variables, under natural scenarios, and evaluate the
110 influence of modifications in the design of the fishways regarding the necessities of the
111 target species, making possible the improvement of fishways efficiency. The above is
112 summarized in the main following contributions: (i) new definition of calculus
113 equations for SNOF under uniform and non-uniform performance; (ii) evaluation and
114 validation of predictability of water levels of the proposed equations; (iii) theoretical
115 demonstration of the use of the defined equations and algorithm to improve the

116 fishway efficiency.

117 2. Materials and methods

118 2.1. Fishway description

119 The experiments were conducted in a real-scale SNOF with a design discharge of 0.278
120 m³/s (Fig. 1). This structure is located in the Tormes River near the village of La Flecha
121 (Salamanca, Spain) and it is characterized by small deviances from design parameters
122 (± 0.010 m) (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2010). The average topographic difference between
123 cross-walls ($\Delta\bar{Z}$) is 0.247 m, that is to say, it has an average slope [$\bar{S} = \Delta\bar{Z}/(\bar{L} + \bar{e})$,
124 where \bar{L} stands for the length of the pool and \bar{e} for the thickness of the cross-wall] of
125 0.088 m/m (Fig. 2). Cross-walls consist on an alternative succession of submerged
126 hydrodynamic notches [mean width (\bar{b}_n) of 0.310 m and mean height of the sill (\bar{p}) of
127 0.917 m] and bottom orifices [mean width \bar{b}_o of 0.197 m and mean height (\bar{a}_o) of
128 0.191 m].

130 **Fig. 2.** Location and schematic representation of the studied SNOF in La Flecha (Salamanca,
131 Spain). Numbers 1 to 9 indicate the nine cross-walls used in this study.

132 The geometrical parameters were measured by topographic surveying with a total
133 station Leica TC307 to a precision of 0.001 m. Smaller details, such as orifice and notch
134 dimensions, were measured by means of a metal ruler to the same precision level. The
135 measurement of all individual characteristics was necessary in order to discriminate
136 between the non-uniform performance due to geometrical differences and the non-
137 uniform performance due to water level changes.

138 2.2. Experimental arrangement and experiments

139 Table 1 summarizes all the experiments performed. To determine flow
140 interdependencies between orifices (O) and notches (N), both were studied separately
141 and in combination (NO). In the experimental scenarios where notches or orifices had
142 to be closed, wood covers were used and the junctions with the concrete were
143 completely sealed by means of insulation foam. In those experimental scenarios
144 involving the notch, streaming (S) and plunging (P) regimens were studied. For each
145 combination above (O, N.S., N.P., NO.S. and NO.P.) three different discharge regimes
146 were studied: low (L), high (H), and medium (M) (Table 1). The discharge was
147 controlled through the gate situated in the upper slot (Fig. 2) and was measured by
148 chemical gaging using Rhodamine WT as tracer (Martínez, 2001). This gate was
149 installed for the maintenance and cleaning of the fishway, and provided the
150 opportunity to achieve different hydrodynamic scenarios in a single season.

151 **Table 1.** Description of the studied scenarios. O: Orifice alone; N: Notch alone; NO: Notch and
 152 orifice together; L: Low discharge; M: Medium discharge; H: High discharge; P: Plunging
 153 performance; S: Streaming performance; P/S: Partly plunging and partly streaming; 1:
 154 Backwater profile; 2: Drawdown profile; U: Uniform profile.

Scenario	Discharge (m ³ /s)	$h_{1,1}$ (m)	$h_{2,9}$ (m)
O.L.2	0.078	1.483	0.860
O.L.U	0.072	1.120	0.861
O.L.1	0.060	1.110	1.447
O.M.2	0.080	1.514	0.987
O.M.U	0.065	1.339	1.090
O.M.1	0.063	1.282	1.481
O.H.U	0.073	1.531	1.298
O.H.1	0.070	1.502	1.485
N.P.L.U	0.077	1.173	0.881
N.P/S.L.1	0.077	1.172	1.503
N.S.M.2	0.135	1.297	0.862
N.S.M.U	0.135	1.292	1.055
N.S.M.1	0.135	1.294	1.467
N.S.H.2	0.242	1.510	1.083
N.S.H.U	0.242	1.507	1.256
N.S.H.1	0.242	1.509	1.440
NO.P.L.U	0.078	0.992	0.795
NO.P/S.L.1	0.078	0.994	1.472
NO.P.M.U	0.095	1.065	0.827
NO.P/S.M.1	0.095	1.066	1.466
NO.P.H.U	0.131	1.141	0.912
NO.P/S.H.1	0.131	1.141	1.475
NO.S.L.U	0.151	1.195	1.040
NO.S.L.1	0.151	1.190	1.488
NO.S.M.U	0.195	1.306	1.097
NO.S.M.1	0.195	1.299	1.391
NO.S.H.U	0.271	1.455	1.230
NO.S.H.1	0.271	1.458	1.479
NO.S.H.U*	0.337	1.519	1.255

*Extra scenario taking advantage of the high river flow recorded while the experiments were carried out.

155

156 The study was conducted in nine cross-walls located upstream, after the control gate
 157 and a transition weir (Fig. 2). The turning pool was adapted to allow the artificial
 158 modification of the water level to achieve uniform profiles (U) (same depth in all
 159 pools), as well as non-uniform profiles which include conceptual backwater profiles (1)

160 (higher depths upstream) and drawdown profiles (2) (higher depths downstream)
161 (Rajaratnam et al., 1986; Chow, 2004; Fuentes-Pérez et al., 2014).

162 After excluding nearly impossible scenarios, due to the complexity required to reach
163 them in real fishways (e.g. backwater profiles in NO experiments), twenty nine
164 scenarios were studied (Table 1). The water level was measured to a millimetric
165 precision in each cross-wall by means of metal rulers installed downstream and in the
166 opposite site of the notches, where the water surface is more stable (Fig. 2). The water
167 level oscillations were recorded for 8 seconds using a camera (Cannon EOS 600D) with
168 a sampling rate of 25 Hz; in all the cases a stable mean value was obtained after two
169 seconds (50 samples).

170 2.3. Discharge equations

171 There are different ways to interpret the operation of SNOFs. Rajaratnam et al. (1988,
172 1989), following earlier works on vertical slot fishways (Rajaratnam et al., 1986) and
173 baffle fishways (Rajaratnam and Katopodis, 1984), proposed the use of dimensionless
174 relationships to describe their performance. These equations have been widely proven
175 and reaffirmed (Ead et al., 2004; Yagci, 2010). However, according to the formula
176 employed, they are independent of the h_2 of each cross-wall and, therefore, they are
177 only valid for uniform operational conditions. It is also possible to use the classical
178 equations for weirs to interpret the operation of SNOFs (Martínez de Azagra, 1999;
179 FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier, 2002a; Santos et al., 2012). In this case, discharge through
180 a notch (Q_n) is described using the equation for weirs proposed by Poleni (1717)
181 together with a discharge coefficient that describes the working conditions under
182 plunging performance (C_p), and another coefficient that reflects the effect

183 (contractions and upstream discharge influence) of the streaming performance (C_s)
 184 (Eq. 1). In addition, the discharge through submerged orifices (Q_o) is described by the
 185 equation derived from Bernoulli's principle together with a discharge coefficient that
 186 takes into account the effect of contractions and expansions (C_o) (Eq. 2). In both
 187 equations g stands for gravity.

$$188 \quad Q_n = \frac{2}{3} \cdot C_p \cdot C_s \cdot b_n \cdot (h_1 - p)^{1.5} \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g} \quad (1)$$

$$189 \quad Q_o = C_o \cdot b_o \cdot a_o \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g \cdot \Delta H} \quad (2)$$

190 C_p is usually defined by Rehbock's equation for free discharge sharp-crested
 191 rectangular weirs without contractions [application range: $0.05 \leq (h_1 - p) \leq 0.80$ and 0.01
 192 $\leq p \leq 1.00$] (Eq. 3) (Rehbock, 1929; Kim, 2001; Ead et al., 2004) or by a constant
 193 coefficient (ranging from 0.495 to 0.750, where usually a value of 0.600 is selected for
 194 design purpose) (Rajaratnam et al., 1988; Martínez de Azagra, 1999; FAO/DVWK, 2002;
 195 Larinier, 2002a). C_s takes into account the performance of the notches in submerged
 196 conditions, thus, generally the equation for sharp-crested rectangular weir proposed
 197 by Villemonte (1947) is used (Eq. 4, $\beta_0 = 1.000$ and $\beta_1 = 0.385$) [application range: $0 \leq$
 198 $(h_2 - p)/(h_1 - p) \leq 0.90$] (Martínez de Azagra, 1999; FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier, 2002a). C_s
 199 will be equal to 1 when the notch works under plunging performance.

$$200 \quad C_p = 0.605 + \frac{1}{1000 \cdot (h_1 - p)} + 0.08 \cdot \left(\frac{h_1 - p}{p} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$201 \quad C_s = \beta_0 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{h_2 - p}{h_1 - p} \right)^{1.5} \right]^{\beta_1} \quad (4)$$

202 2.4. Water level calculation

203 To simulate the water level distributions in SNOFs under different scenarios, it is
204 necessary to take into account the specific geometrical characteristics of each pool and
205 cross-wall. After defining these characteristics, an iterative bottom-up calculation can
206 be carried out considering boundary conditions: the discharge through the fishway or
207 the headwater level (upstream water level in the first cross-wall considered, $h_{1,1}$), and
208 $h_{2,n}$ (where n is the number of cross-walls studied or in the fishway). A complete
209 definition of this algorithm is explained in Fuentes-Pérez et al. (2014).

210 2.5. Validation

211 The fit of the proposed discharge equations has been evaluated using r-squared (R^2),
212 as well as variance of observed and predicted values [$\sigma^2 = \text{RSS}/(n-2)$, where RSS is the
213 residual sum of squares] and graphical validation. The comparison of the predicted
214 water level profiles has been carried out by comparing the mean relative errors (MRE)
215 for each scenario as well as by checking water level distributions.

216 **3. Experimental results and discussion**

217 3.1. Discharge coefficients

218 Traditionally, the same discharge coefficients have been used for the design of both
219 fishways and weirs. However, the performance of fishways is different mainly due to
220 the slope, thickness of cross-walls, contractions and the dependency between cross-
221 walls, which will probably cause a different water level distribution. Thus, the classical
222 formulation must be either confirmed or modified.

223 3.1.1. Orifices

224 The study of submerged orifice fishways has demonstrated, for wide a range of
225 operation conditions, that ΔH in all cross-walls remains constant independently of the
226 water levels upstream and downstream the fishway (Boiten and Dommerholt, 2006).
227 This property is derived from Eq. 2 and from the fact that the discharge coefficients
228 only depend on the shape of the submerged orifice and the thickness of the cross-
229 walls, remaining constant for different water levels.

230 The above described performance has also been observed in the fishway studied here.
231 For all orifice experiments (ΔH from 0.176 m to 0.324 m), the discharge coefficient (C_o
232 $\pm SD = 0.876 \pm 0.050$) was independent from the water levels of each cross-wall (h_1 , h_2 ,
233 and ΔH). The values obtained agree with the values observed by other authors
234 (Larinier, 2002a; Boiten and Dommerholt, 2006). Likewise, C_o shows a small correlation
235 with the dimension of the orifice ($a_o \cdot b_o$) and Q_o . This is due to the fact that, since C_o is
236 independent to the water level variables, the simplifications from orifice dimension
237 measuring and fishway discharges (chemical gaging) are transmitted directly to C_o . The
238 cross-walls were built *in situ* with concrete, which produced geometrical irregularities
239 that cannot be characterized with the geometrical variables used in the calculation (a_o
240 and b_o). These irregularities are greater in orifices than in notches, due to their position
241 near the rough bed and their small dimensions. Since these deviations are not
242 considered in a_o and b_o measures, they are translated to variance in C_o .

243 The observed properties in submerged orifices make them of particular interest to
244 design fishways with autonomous water drop compensation. However, they can suffer
245 from inappropriate attractions or locating difficulty, obstructions, and the drawbacks

246 of trapping floating debris (FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier, 2002a). Likewise, some fish
247 species may be reluctant to use them [e.g. American shad (*Alosa sapidissima*) (Larinier,
248 2002a)] or may prefer other types of connections between pools [e.g. Iberian chub
249 (Branco et al., 2013) or Iberian nase (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015b)].

250 3.1.2. Notches

251 Although orifices are important to maintain the fishways clean of sediments and to
252 allow the pass of certain fish species (Larinier, 2002a), generally the most important
253 fraction of discharge will flow through the notch. To differentiate between plunging
254 and streaming effects, and to determine the independency between notches and
255 orifices, first, taking into account the calculated C_o , Q_o was deducted from combined
256 notch and orifice experiments. Then, the coefficients for the submerged equation (β_0
257 and β_1 in Eq. 4) were determined from observed data, as recommended by Villemonte
258 (1947) [Fig. 3(b)]. In order to do this, only the data from submerged notches were
259 used, obtaining a first approximation for the coefficients, where β_0 can be considered a
260 constant approximation of C_p . To evaluate the distribution of C_p , the first
261 approximation for C_s was deducted from all data (dividing the data by the estimated
262 C_s). This demonstrated that the distribution of C_p depends on h_1 , and describes an
263 exponential model with a decelerated increase of the coefficient that approaches a
264 horizontal asymptote [Fig. 3(a)]. Finally, the observed models for discharge coefficients
265 were fitted together, using all the data, to obtain the final expressions (Fig. 3, Eq. 5 and
266 Eq. 6).

$$267 \quad C_p = 0.689 \cdot \left[1 - e^{-3.889 \cdot (h_1 - \rho)} \right] \quad (5)$$

268

$$C_s = \left[1 - \left(\frac{h_2 - p}{h_1 - p} \right)^{1.5} \right]^{0.331} \quad (6)$$

269

270 **Fig. 3.** Fits of the discharge coefficients for the notches. a) Discharge coefficient for the
271 plunging regimen (C_p). b) Discharge coefficient for the streaming regimen (C_s).

272 Fig. 3 shows that notch data for both set of experiments (notches together with
273 orifices and notches alone) can be explained by the same equations, demonstrating
274 that the performance of orifices and notches can be considered independent for the
275 estimation of water level distribution. Likewise, even if independent fits for each set
276 are considered, the same mean variance is obtained (0.003).

277 The C_p model differs from the values and equations proposed by other authors
278 (Rehbock, 1929; Rajaratnam et al., 1989; Martínez de Azagra, 1999; FAO/DVWK, 2002;
279 Larinier, 2002a; Ead et al., 2004); however, its performance has a logical explanation.
280 The coefficient must be 0 when $h_1 - p \leq 0$, then, when the discharge starts, the influence
281 of the sill is big producing a small C_p . As h_1 increases, sill influence remains almost
282 constant, producing a decelerated progressive increase of C_p . Likewise, the kinetic
283 influence of the cross-wall situated upstream, for first stages of the discharge (low h_1),
284 is negligible. It is worth mentioning that the measuring error in the experiments

285 increases at lower discharges (lower C_p values) due to a greater influence of the
286 geometrical measure precision, as well as the nature of the chemical gaging and the
287 lower mixing power in pools. As the water height increases, C_p will approach a
288 horizontal asymptote with a value in the range suggested by other specialized
289 references (Martínez de Azagra, 1999; FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier, 2002a).

290 Regarding C_s , most of the guides for fishway design recommend Eq. 4, which uses the
291 coefficients proposed by Villemonte (1947) for rectangular weirs ($\beta_0 = 1.000$ and $\beta_1 =$
292 0.385) (Martínez de Azagra, 1999; Larinier, 2002a; FAO/DVWK, 2002). However,
293 despite the fit being considerably good [Fig 3(b), $R^2=0.821$], as recommended by
294 Villemonte, these coefficients should be calculated or evaluated for each
295 configuration. The proposed new relations suggest that for the same scenario, there is
296 a smaller influence of C_s (a greater value) than in Villemonte's experiments due to the
297 different conditions in the fishway (possibly due to a different slope or smaller water
298 path than the one used by the author).

299 The observed difference between the data and the proposed model, as argued in the
300 previous section, seems to be related mainly to the simplification of geometrical
301 variables and chemical gaging. This becomes more obvious when comparing
302 experimental data from notches, with data from notches together with orifices (Fig. 3).
303 The variance of NO experiments is greater (0.005 vs 0.001) because the geometrical
304 simplification of the orifices is also involved in the estimation of C_p and C_s . However, as
305 described in the next section, the deviations in the estimation of water level
306 distribution as a result of this variance will be rather small.

307 3.2. Depth profiles and applications

308 With equations able to predict the water level distribution in non-uniform scenarios, it
 309 will be possible to model the performance of fishways under dynamic situations and
 310 adapt their operation to new conditions, improving, when necessary, the attraction
 311 efficiency [number of fish that are able to find the entrance (Bunt et al., 2012)] and
 312 passage efficiency [number of fish exited of those that entered in the fishway (Bunt et
 313 al., 2012)] and, thus, achieving a higher fishway efficiency during longer periods of
 314 time.

315 The proposed equations (Eq. 5 and Eq. 6) together with the algorithm described in
 316 Fuentes-Pérez et al. (2014) are able to estimate water level distributions with a high
 317 degree of precision in all the studied scenarios (Table 2 and Fig. 4). In all cases, the
 318 maximum MRE was registered in orifices when working alone (Table 2). This, as it was
 319 discussed previously, is explained by the observed variance in the discharge
 320 coefficient. Despite this, the deviations are small, higher in ΔH distributions because of
 321 the normalization of the error [Fig. 4(b)]

322 **Table 2.** MRE (%) for the studied scenarios with the proposed equations.

Scenario	Notch and orifices			Notch			Orifices			Mean		
	h_1	h_2	ΔH	h_1	h_2	ΔH	h_1	h_2	ΔH	h_1	h_2	ΔH
Uniform	1.74	1.93	3.79	0.84	0.84	3.70	4.40	4.97	9.36	1.96	2.17	4.69
Backwater	1.36	1.52	7.17	0.66	0.65	4.89	4.12	3.85	9.30	1.88	1.88	7.13
Drawdown	-	-	-	0.68	0.66	4.23	8.25	9.13	10.03	4.46	4.89	7.13
Mean	1.57	1.74	5.35	0.73	0.72	4.28	5.38	5.68	9.53	2.28	2.43	6.09

323

324

325 **Fig. 4.** Water level distributions in the 9 studied cross-walls of the fishway. a) Observed and
 326 estimated h_1 profiles for 3 of the 29 scenarios. b) Observed and estimated ΔH profiles for 3 of
 327 the 29 scenarios.

328 When the fishway is placed correctly [i.e. in the attractive areas for fish (Larinier,
 329 2002b)], first, the fish will need to find the fishway entrance in order to pass it. To
 330 accomplish this, the entrance needs to strike a compromise between attracting the
 331 fish and enabling them to enter (Bunt, 2001; Larinier, 2002b; Williams et al., 2012).
 332 Non-uniform performances, produced by changes in headwater or tailwater levels, will
 333 modify the hydraulic conditions in the entrance from the ones defined during the
 334 design process, causing backwater or drawdown profiles. Backwater profiles are
 335 produced by decreasing tailwater or increasing headwater levels. These can generate
 336 excessive ΔH in most downstream cross-walls, increasing velocities [the expected
 337 maximum velocity is $\sqrt{2\Delta Hg}$ (Rajaratnam et al., 1986; Larinier, 2002a; Liu et al.,
 338 2006)], turbulence, noise or oxygenation. Although in a first instant this can increase
 339 the attraction (Williams et al., 2012), entrance can be limited according to the
 340 swimming speed of the migrating species involved or the produced turbulence, and
 341 sometimes it will require the fish to jump to enter, reducing or impeding its use for
 342 some species (Bunt et al., 2012). For instance, Branco et al. (2013) and Sanz-Ronda et

343 al. (2015b) observed a reduced use of notches for Iberian chub, Iberian barbel and
344 Iberian nase, when the fishway entrance was working in plunging regimens. Regarding
345 velocity limits at the entrance, Larinier (2002b) defines an optimal water speed for
346 salmonids and large migrants in the order of 2.0 m/s to 2.4 m/s ($\Delta H = 0.2-0.3$ m).
347 Similar values can be considered for species with comparable swimming capacities
348 such as Iberian barbel and Iberian nase (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015a).

349 The backwater profile created by the increase in headwater level can be managed, for
350 instance by designing a first cross-wall (the most upstream one) with a gate and, after
351 this, some cross-walls without ΔZ between them. Likewise, backwater profile created
352 by the decreases of the tailwater level can be managed by decreasing the sill of the
353 downstream notches or installing submerged pre-barrages that will absorb the
354 reduction of the water level. However, the latter is not a probable scenario as the
355 fishway should be designed to work under the reasonably highest difference between
356 the headwater and tailwater levels of the obstacles (Wang, 2008).

357 Regarding drawdown profiles, they occur when the tailwater level increases or
358 headwater level decreases. However, in most cases, the headwater level will remain
359 more or less constant (Larinier, 2002a). These profiles decrease the ΔH in most
360 downstream cross-walls, reducing, among others, the velocity at the entrance, which,
361 in turn, can produce a diminution on the attraction efficiency. Larinier (2002b)
362 recommends at minimum velocity of 1 m/s at the entrance. In both cases, these issues
363 can be solved by increasing the sill elevation of the most downstream notch or
364 increasing the discharge input in the most downstream pool.

365 It is possible to use the proposed equations and calculation process to model all

366 defined performances, and design specific solutions (as mentioned above). However,
 367 as the fishway should be designed to work under the reasonably highest difference
 368 between water levels, and as the headwater level in most cases will not change
 369 significantly, the most probable scenario will be the drawdown profile where tailwater
 370 level increases. Fig. 5(a) shows the simulation of the defined two options to improve
 371 the attraction of a drawdown profile for the studied fishway, that is, the elevation of
 372 the sill of the most downstream cross-wall ($p + 0.550$ m) and the increase of the
 373 discharge input in the last pool ($Q + 0.250$ m³/s). Both solutions will increase the final
 374 ΔH to reach to the desired value.

375

376 Figure 5. Examples of use of the proposed equations to improve efficiency of the fishways. a)
 377 Distribution of h_1 and ΔH in an attraction optimization example with 2 options to improve the
 378 use of a fishway with drawdown profile (boundary conditions: $Q = 0.200$ m³/s and $h_{2,9} = 1.600$
 379 m). b) modification of h_1 , ΔH and VDP, in a fishway with higher ΔZ (≈ 0.30 m) between cross-

380 walls 3 and 4, and 4 and 5 after the increase of sill height in downstream cross-walls (from p_3
381 to $p_9 + 0.05, +0.10, +0.12, +0.08, +0.06, +0.04, +0.02$ m, respectively) (boundary conditions: $Q =$
382 $0.271 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $h_{2,9} = 1.230$ m).

383 Once fish have entered to the fishway, its internal hydraulic performance will
384 determinate the passage efficiency. Usually, at practical and design level, two main
385 factors should be considered when evaluating the internal performance: ΔH between
386 adjacent pools and the volumetric dissipation power (VDP). It is possible to estimate
387 both variables with the proposed equations, as VDP only depends on the pool
388 geometry, and the calculated variables [$VDP = Q \cdot \Delta H \cdot g \cdot \rho / (h_0 \cdot B \cdot L)$ where ρ is the water
389 density (kg/m^3)] (FAO/DVWK, 2002; Larinier, 2002a; Towler et al., 2015). VDP will
390 provide an indication of average pool turbulence and ΔH can be considered as an
391 indicative of the maximum velocity that the fish will need to overcome.

392 VDP should be maintained under certain levels according to the target species, fishway
393 type and type of pools (step pool, resting pool or turning pool) (Towler et al., 2015). It
394 is roughly correlated with more complex parameters (such as velocity field, turbulence
395 or shear stress levels within the pool), which, in turn, are strongly correlated with fish
396 preferences. For instance, several studies have observed that, within a pool, the
397 Iberian barbel has preference for areas with lower velocities, turbulence and shear
398 stress (Silva et al., 2011; Silva et al., 2012; Alexandre et al., 2013).

399 The maximum velocity to be overcome by the fish, directly related with ΔH , will occur
400 in the cross-walls. This fact has been shown for example in electromyogram telemetry
401 studies that revealed that Iberian barbels reached the maximum swimming speed
402 during the orifice passage within a pool-weir fishway (Alexandre et al., 2013). After

403 surpassing the cross-wall is believed that the fish rest, if necessary, within the
404 recirculation areas of the pools before facing to the next cross-wall (Silva et al., 2011;
405 Alexandre et al., 2013).

406 Thus, each cross-wall can be seen as a small obstacle that fish will need to surpass
407 taking advantage of its abilities and the resting area. In this sense, local design or
408 constructing failures inside the fishway could reduce fish passage. By modeling the
409 internal performance of a fishway, it is possible to compensate for any possible
410 drawbacks. For instance, Fig. 5(b) simulates a deviation in ΔZ (real $\Delta Z + 0.05$ m)
411 between cross-walls 3 and 4, and 4 and 5, and shows one of the possible solutions. The
412 deviation of ΔZ will produce the increment of VDP and ΔH from the recommended
413 ones for the target species in the upstream pools, which could be a limiting factor for
414 passage. However, by using the proposed equations and bottom-up calculations, it is
415 possible to design a solution (in this case the increase of downstream notches sill
416 height) to compensate for these errors, reducing both, ΔH and VDP .

417 **4. Summary and conclusions**

418 In this article, a modification of the discharge equations for submerged notch and
419 orifice fishways is proposed. Its formulation differs from the classical method because
420 (a) the equations have been specifically adapted to fishways and (b) non-uniform
421 scenarios have also been studied. The equations fit the observed data and, for most
422 common design conditions, suggest higher discharge coefficients than the traditional
423 values and equations used. Likewise, a new logical distribution pattern for C_p has been
424 detected, observed, and modeled.

425 The discharge equations together with a logical bottom-up iterative calculation are

426 able to correctly model the performance of fishways under different regimens, and
427 uniform and non-uniform scenarios. This will allow to create specific solutions for
428 changing scenarios or when building errors are detected.

429 This work also exposes the necessity to specifically adapt the classical design equations
430 to fishways in order to model correctly the hydraulic parameters (ΔH , h_o , VDP , etc.)
431 that might limit their use. The correct modeling and interpretation could be used to
432 design more accurate and better adapted solutions, to determine whether a fishway
433 has hydraulic constraints which could compromise its efficiency, and to adapt or
434 correct fishways when necessary.

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439 **6. Notation**

440 The following symbols are used in this paper:

441 a_o = height of the orifice (m)

442 B = pool width (m)

443 b_n = notch width (m)

444 b_o = orifice width (m)

445 C_o = discharge coefficient for orifices

446 C_p = discharge coefficient for the plunging regimen

447 C_s = discharge coefficient for the streaming regimen

448 e = thickness of the cross-wall (m)

449 g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2)

450 h_0 = mean water level of the flow in the pool in relation to the center of the

451 pool (m)

452 h_1 = mean water level of the flow in the pool in relation to the upstream of

453 the notch (m)

454 $h_{1,i}$ = mean water level of the flow in the pool in relation to the upstream of

455 the notch in the cross-wall number i (m)

456 h_2 = mean water level of the flow in the pool in relation to the downstream

457 of the notch (m)

458 $h_{2,i}$ = mean water level of the flow in the pool in relation to the downstream

459 of the notch in the cross-wall number i (m)

460 i = cross-wall number

461 L = pool length (m)

462 n = total number of cross-walls

463 p = sill height (m)

464 Q = discharge or flow rate ($Q = Q_n + Q_o$ for combined scenarios) (m^3/s)

465 Q_n = discharge through notches (m^3/s)

466 Q_o = discharge through orifices (m^3/s)

467 R^2 = determination coefficient

468 S = slope of the fishway (m/m)

469 VDP = volumetric dissipation power (W/m^3)

470 β_0, β_1 = dimensionless coefficients for Eq. (4)

471 ΔH = difference in water level between pools or head drop ($\Delta H = h_1 - h_2$) (m)

472 ΔZ = topographic difference between cross-walls (m)

473 ρ = density of water (kg/m³)

474 σ^2 = variance

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